

ISSN (p): 3030-3362

№ 6 (28)

27.06.2025

IF 2024
11.7

R

TADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation

scientific-methodical journal

S C I E N C E S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

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Languages:

Uzbek, Russian, English and
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Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
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Jismoniy madaniyatning pedagogik asoslari

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada jismoniy madaniyatning pedagogik asoslari yoritilgan bo'lib, o'quvchilarda sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish, ularni ijtimoiy jihatdan faol shaxs sifatida tarbiyalash va mustaqil jismoniy faoliyat ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan yondashuvlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy madaniyat, pedagogik asoslar, sog'lom turmush tarzi, jismoniy tarbiya, amaliylik, individualizatsiya, differentsiatsiya, ta'lim integratsiyasi, tarbiyaviy ta'sir, mustaqil mashg'ulotlar, baholash, sport pedagogikasi, jismoniy rivojlanish, metodika, sog'lom avlod.

Педагогические основы физической культуры

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются педагогические основы физической культуры, анализируются подходы, направленные на формирование здорового образа жизни у студентов, воспитание их как социально активных личностей, развитие навыков самостоятельной двигательной активности.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, педагогические основы, здоровый образ жизни, физическое воспитание, практичность, индивидуализация, дифференциация, образовательная интеграция, воспитательное воздействие, самостоятельная подготовка, оценка, спортивная педагогика, физическое развитие, методика, здоровое поколение.

Pedagogical foundations of physical education

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Abstract: The article examines the pedagogical foundations of physical education, analyzes approaches aimed at forming a healthy lifestyle in students, educating them as socially active individuals, developing skills of independent motor activity.

Keywords: physical education, pedagogical foundations, healthy lifestyle, physical education, practicality, individualization, differentiation, educational integration, educational impact, independent preparation, assessment, sports pedagogy, physical development, methodology, healthy generation.

Kirish.

Jismoniy madaniyat ta'lim-tarbiya tizimining ajralmas qismi bo'lib, u nafaqat sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish, balki shaxsning har tomonlama rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi. Pedagogik asoslar jismoniy tarbiya jarayonini samarali tashkil etish, individual yondashuvni yo'lga qo'yish, tarbiyaviy ta'sirni kuchaytirish hamda mustahkam amaliy tayyorgarlikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Mazkur maqolada jismoniy madaniyatning pedagogik yo'nalishlari, ularning ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va amaliy samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi.

Jismoniy madaniyatning pedagogik asoslari — bu jismoniy tarbiya va sport faoliyatini tashkil etish, boshqarish, rejalashtirish va baholashda qo'llaniladigan nazariy va amaliy yondashuvlar, prinsiplar hamda metodlar majmuasidir. Ushbu asoslar o'quvchilar va sportchilarni har tomonlama jismoniy rivojlantirish, sog'lom turmush tarziga o'rgatish, ularning jismoniy-madaniy saviyasini oshirish, shuningdek, mustaqil faoliyatga yo'naltirishga qaratilgan.

1. Individualizatsiya va differentsiatsiya

O'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanish darajasi, yosh xususiyatlari, jinsiy farqlari, sog'lig'i holati va qiziqishlarini hisobga olgan holda ta'limni tashkil etish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu yondashuv o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshiradi va har bir shaxs uchun mos va xavfsiz mashg'ulot sharoitini yaratadi.

2. Amaliylikka yo'naltirish

Jismoniy tarbiyada nazariy bilimlar amaliy mashg'ulotlar orqali mustahkamlanadi. Sport o'yinlari, jismoniy mashqlar, trenajyorlar bilan ishlash, ochiq havodagi faoliyatlar orqali o'quvchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarligi va ko'nikmalari rivojlantiriladi.

3. Tarbiyaviy ta'sir

Jismoniy tarbiya nafaqat jismoniy rivojlanishga, balki ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyaga ham xizmat qiladi. O'qituvchi va murabbiylar o'quvchilarda irodalilik, fidoyilik, jamoada ishlash, mas'uliyat hissi, o'ziga ishonch kabi fazilatlarni shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

4. Fanlararo integratsiya

Jismoniy madaniyat boshqa fanlar, ayniqsa biologiya, anatomiya, fiziologiya, gigiyena, psixologiya va matematika bilan uzviy bog'langan. Bu yondashuv orqali o'quvchilar o'zining jismoniy imkoniyatlarini ilmiy asosda anglashga va baholashga o'rganadi.

5. Maqsadga yo'naltirilgan rejalashtirish

Har bir mashg'ulot aniq maqsad asosida rejalashtiriladi va o'quvchilarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirishga yo'naltiriladi. Rejalashtirishda sport turlari xususiyatlari, dars davomiyligi, yuklama darajasi va dam olish intervallari e'tiborga olinadi.

6. Moslashtirilgan o'qitish

Turli yoshdagi, jismoniy imkoniyatlari har xil bo'lgan o'quvchilar uchun moslashtirilgan ta'lim metodlari qo'llaniladi. Bu orqali har bir o'quvchiga shaxsiy yondashuv asosida rivojlanish imkoniyati yaratiladi.

7. Mustaqil mashg'ulotlarga o'rgatish

O'quvchilarda mustaqil jismoniy faoliyat olib borish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish muhim hisoblanadi. Ularga mashg'ulot dasturlarini tuzish, o'zini nazorat qilish, xavfsizlik qoidalariga rioya etish kabi ko'nikmalar beriladi. Bu esa ularni hayot davomida sog'lom turmush tarzini saqlashga undaydi.

8. Baholash va natijalarga asoslangan takomillashtirish

O'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishi doimiy monitoring va diagnostika asosida baholanadi. Bu baholash natijalariga ko'ra o'qitish mazmuni va metodikasi takomillashtirilib boriladi. Objektiv baholash usullari orqali o'quvchilarning rivojlanish dinamikasi aniqlanadi

Ushbu pedagogik asoslar jismoniy tarbiya jarayonining samaradorligini oshirish, o'quvchilarda sog'lom turmush tarziga bo'lgan ehtiyojni shakllantirish va ularni jismoniy faollikka yo'naltirishda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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Jurnal haqida

“Tadqiq va tadbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali Fer-Teach MChJ tomonidan tashkil etilgan. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023 yil 3 mayda №078777 raqam bilan ro‘yxatga olingan.

ISSN 3030-3362

Jurnalda texnologiya sohasidagi ixtisoslashtirilgan jurnal bo‘lib, texnik fanlarning turli sohalari: fizika, matematika, axborot texnologiyalari bo‘yicha tadqiqot va ishlanmalarning barcha asosiy yo‘nalishlarini qamrab oladi. Jurnalda tilshunoslik, o‘qitish metodikasi va texnika fanlarining rivojlanish tarixiga oid ilmiy maqolalar ham chop etiladi.

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Tillar: o‘zbek, rus, ingliz, qoraqalpoq

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Научно-методический журнал «Исследования и внедрение» учрежден ООО «FerTeach». Данный журнал зарегистрирован номером № 078777 Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан от 3 мая 2023 года.

ISSN 3030-3362

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The scientific and methodological journal "Research and Implementation" was founded by Fer-Teach LLC. This journal is registered under number 078777 by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2023.

ISSN 3030-3362

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